

ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY ASSESSMENT OF A STIRLING CYCLE HIGH-TEMPERATURE HEAT PUMP (SC-HTHP): A PRELIMINARY LCA PERSPECTIVE

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ABSTRACT

Heat pumps that utilize renewable electricity and low-temperature waste heat to generate high-temperature heat are widely recognized as a key technology for lowering carbon dioxide emissions in industrial applications. Recent studies on Stirling Cycle-based High-Temperature Heat Pumps (SC-HTHPs) are driven by their potential to solve global environmental and energy challenges. This study presents a cradle-to-gate Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) of an SC-HTHP, a key component of the SUSHEAT European project, designed to achieve temperatures up to 250°C. The cradle-to-gate LCA conducted in this study assesses the environmental footprint of the HTHP up to its departure from the factory without considering its use during operation by customers and end-of-life treatment processes. The assessment, carried out using SimaPro software and the Ecoinvent database, incorporates data supplied by the Enerin company located in Norway. The analysis used one SC-HTHP unit as the functional unit, employing the ReCiPe 2016 Endpoint method to comprehensively evaluate a wide range of environmental impact indicators. The results demonstrate that the manufacturing phase of the SC-HTHP has a greater environmental impact compared to the transportation phase. Throughout both phases, the most substantial impact is observed in human health, ecosystems, and resources. Furthermore, a comparative analysis of air, sea, and road transportation methods indicates that road transport from suppliers to the manufacturing facility results in the highest environmental impact across all three impact categories. Based on the results obtained, steel constitutes the largest portion of the total environmental impact of the materials used in the heat pump components analyzed in this study. Additionally, the greatest environmental impact of the HTHP system studied, across both the manufacturing and transport phases, is associated with fossil resource scarcity in the manufacturing phase. These findings provide valuable insights for optimizing production processes and reducing the environmental footprint of SC-HTHP manufacturing. Further research is required to explore the potential of the SC-HTHPs in decarbonizing the industrial sector by integrating waste heat, solar energy, and diverse energy mix strategies.

Keywords: Stirling Cycle-Based High-Temperature Heat Pump, LCA, Environmental impact, Sustainability, Human Health

1 INTRODUCTION

Decarbonizing production in industrial sectors is essential for meeting the climate goals of the European Union (EU). In the EU, approximately two-thirds of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions in the industrial sectors stem from the use of fossil fuels for heat and electricity generation (Marcos *et al.*, 2024). Governments worldwide are increasingly adopting the Paris Agreement under the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change, incorporating its goals into their national strategies to reach net-zero carbon emissions by 2050 (Kantzas *et al.*, 2022). The European Green Deal outlines the EU's climate goals, aiming for a 55% reduction in CO₂ emissions by 2030 (relative to 1990 levels) and

achieving carbon neutrality by 2050 (Zeilerbauer *et al.*, 2023). These targets will also influence industrial sectors through measures like the European Union's emissions trading system, posing challenges due to the sector's high energy intensity. Industries like paper, food processing, chemicals, and machinery often require high-temperature water, steam, or air for drying, pasteurizing, heating, and distillation processes. These are typically generated by fossil fuel boilers or electric heating, which are energy-inefficient and emit high levels of emissions (Dai *et al.*, 2023).

Renewable Energy Systems (RES) have been deployed as an alternative to fossil fuels to mitigate global warming and reduce greenhouse gas emissions (Aresti *et al.*, 2022). Heat pump systems are an advanced technology that offers an efficient solution for high-temperature heating. They serve as a sustainable alternative to non-renewable fossil fuel-based systems like traditional boilers, significantly improving energy efficiency and reducing the GHG emissions of heating systems (Mateu-Royo *et al.*, 2021; Luo *et al.*, 2020). Heat pumps utilize an external energy source to transfer heat from low-temperature sources to areas with higher temperatures (Lund, and Tóth, 2020). Additionally, when the demand for high-temperature heat coincides with the availability of nearby low-temperature waste heat, it presents an opportunity to effectively use heat pumps (Marcos *et al.*, 2024). In other words, High-Temperature Heat Pumps (HTHPs) are regarded as more efficient than other power-to-heat alternatives because of their high performance, energy efficiency, and ability to recover and reuse on-site waste heat (Magni *et al.*, 2024). HTHPs can decline equivalent CO₂ emissions in comparison to mechanical compression systems by preventing the application of polluting refrigerants and increasing efficiency (Zühlendorf *et al.*, 2019). In recent years, this technology has also garnered significant attention from both the scientific community and the industrial sector. Several research projects are also dedicated to developing HTHPs capable of operating with sink temperatures ranging from 160°C to 200°C, although their commercial availability is expected to take a few more years (Institute for Sustainable Process Technology, 2020; DryEfficiency Project, 2020). Enerin company provides HTHPs that use helium as the working fluid medium and feature double-acting piston compressors in a Stirling cycle. This setup allows for flexible operating conditions, large lifting capacities, and achieving temperatures above 200°C (Høeg *et al.*, 2024).

The environmental impacts of a heating system, such as HTHPs, are influenced not only by its operational lifespan but also by the effects of its materials and components during the manufacturing, use and disposal stages. Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) is a key and effective decision-making tool that complements other methods, which are crucial for promoting more sustainable consumption and production (Patiño *et al.*, 2016). Anyway, LCA methodology assesses the potential environmental impacts of materials and energy flows across various life cycle stages of a product or process, from "cradle to gate" or "cradle to grave" and is commonly used in industrial contexts (Guinee, 2002). The manufacturing stage of a heat pump significantly plays a key role in identifying the environmental impacts throughout its life cycle (HM Government, 2007; Gaujena *et al.*, 2015; Palacios-Lorenzo *et al.*, 2023). However, the significance of this phase in an LCA depends on factors such as the heat pump's type, capacity, key components, and efficiency (Ovchinnikov *et al.*, 2017). Recently, numerous studies have focused on evaluating the LCA of heat pump systems. Fischer *et al.* (2024) applied an LCA method to evaluate the environmental impacts of a residential heat pump system. They discovered that the electricity mix had a substantial effect on the carbon footprint of the supplied heat, reducing it by 48% (Fischer *et al.*, 2024). In the UK, a study evaluated the environmental effects of water-source (WSHP), ground-source (GSHP), air-source (ASHP) heat pumps, and also condensing gas boilers, identifying electricity production for natural gas combustion for boilers and heat pumps as key factors contributing to climate change impacts (Greening and Azapagic, 2012). Heikkilä (2008) evaluated a ground-source heat pump (GSHP) unit for heating and cooling against a traditional air conditioner, showing that the GSHP system offers lower environmental impacts over its lifetime.

According to existing literature, only a limited number of LCA studies have been done on evaluating the environmental sustainability of innovative technologies, such as Stirling Cycle-based High-Temperature Heat Pumps. This research aims to compare various environmental impact categories associated with the manufacturing and transport phases of a Stirling Cycle-based HTHP, a key component of the novel technology developed under the SUSHEAT project to decarbonize heating in industrial sectors. This study seeks to make a meaningful contribution to Norway and the global industrial sectors by advancing renewable energy adoption and offering a valuable resource for

informed decision-making. This paper is structured as follows: Section 2 presents the case study and describes the methodology used for the assessment, detailing the goal, scope, functional unit, and primary data assumptions. It also covers the scenario analyses conducted for the manufacturing and transport phases. Section 3 presents the obtained results of this study and discusses them in the context of existing literature on the decarbonization of industrial systems. Finally, section 4 concludes by summarizing the key findings and providing recommendations for potential directions of future research.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1. Case study

This study examined a Stirling Cycle-based High-Temperature Heat Pump, an innovative system developed as part of the SUSHEAT project. In addition to the HTHP, the EU-funded SUSHEAT system incorporates several innovative technologies, including a Solar Fresnel collector, a bio-inspired Phase Change Material (PCM) Thermal Energy Storage (TES) system, and a control and integration twin (CIT) system as presented in Figure 1. The SUSHEAT system features two TES devices, one for each system loop, the cold and the hot loop. They are particularly useful when high heat demand is low, allowing excess energy to be stored, or when waste heat is unavailable, enabling energy to be extracted from the TES units as needed. Two heat transfer liquid (HTL) buffers are required, one for each system loop, to ensure safety and pressure damping. This setup guarantees full system flexibility, allowing the use of different HTLs across various temperature ranges. SUSHEAT system optimizes heat-upgrading integration by incorporating key components and considering off-the-shelf renewable technologies, like solar Fresnel collectors, to improve feasibility even at low temperatures. It also focuses on harvesting waste heat using solar Fresnel collectors and utilizing ambient heat as a sustainable energy source. Solar energy collectors supply supplementary energy to the system. Depending on the heat demand, either medium or high-temperature collectors can be utilized. In this system, Fresnel collectors, a high-temperature type, are employed to meet energy requirements. This SUSHEAT system is developed to support industrial processes that require high temperatures, typically ranging from 150°C to 250°C, while considering the capabilities of the current SC-HTHPs. The heat pump output used in the LCA is 200 kW, with a working fluid of 40 bar water. To assess the effectiveness of the SUSHEAT concept, two primary case studies were chosen: the dairy industry represented by Mandrekas in Corinth and the fish meal company, namely Pelagia in Bergen, Norway. The SUSHEAT concept can be successfully implemented at Mandrekas Company for dairy operations to fulfill the heating needs of boilers and assist in the homogenization and pressurization processes. Integrating the HTHPs with a Solar Fresnel collector or utilizing ambient heat offers an efficient and sustainable solution for these applications in Mandrekas company. The SUSHEAT system will also be implemented at Pelagia Company to meet High-Temperature demands, providing heat for cookers and dryers. This application will enhance energy efficiency and support the company's heating requirements for these processes. However, according to Figure 1 of the SUSHEAT system, the Pelagia company's system is designed to operate with the Stirling Cycle-based HTHP assisted by waste heat.

Figure 1. SUSHEAT system (Marcos *et al.*, 2024)

2.2. LCA execution

This study utilizes the LCA method to quantify the environmental effects of the selected Stirling Cycle-based HTHP system. LCA involves balancing emissions and waste production with the consumption of resources and energy (ISO 14040, 2006a; ISO 14044, 2006b). Additionally, LCA is a widely recognized and standardized approach for measuring environmental impact, endorsed by the UNEP (UNEP, 2002) and also the European Commission (European Commission, 2001). The LCA analysis comprises four stages, as presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Four primary stages of an LCA

2.2.1. Defining goal, scope and functional unit

The goal of this research study is to assess and compare the environmental effects linked to the manufacturing and transport phase of a Stirling cycle HTHP's life cycle by developing life cycle models. The HTHP, manufactured by the Enerin company in Norway, is a key component of the innovative SUSHEAT system. The scope is a cradle-to-gate analysis. The system boundaries define the unit processes included in the LCA analysis. Figure 3 depicts the general system boundary for the LCA analysis, reflecting the manufacturing phase and transport stage (T1) considered in this study (Zone M).

Figure 3: The system boundary of LCA for the Stirling Cycle HTHP applied in this study (zone M: cradle-to-gate)

Manufacturing stage: This stage is the materials production phase, including the raw materials extraction and the manufacturing process. Additionally, this study conducted the environmental impact analysis using the LCA approach until the use/operational phase. In this paper, the transportation of raw materials to the manufacturing site is considered in another LCA analysis scenario. The functional unit (FU) is defined as a Stirling cycle-based High-Temperature Heat Pump unit. The LCA results are presented based on the functional unit.

2.2.2. Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) Data

For carrying out the LCA in this study, data is primarily sourced from the Ecoinvent database (version 3.10), with additional information provided by the Enerin company.

2.2.2.1. Inventory data for the manufacturing phase

LCIA is a stage of the LCA process where the inputs and outputs of a product or system are compiled across its entire life cycle. The system selected for this study is a Stirling Cycle-based High-Temperature Heat Pump. It is worth mentioning that this research adopts a cradle-to-gate approach, excluding both the use stage and the end-of-life stage as part of the LCA. Additionally, no installation of the HTHP for the SUSHEAT project has taken place at the end-user sites of the two companies involved: Pelagia, located in Bergen, Norway, and Mandrekas, located in Corinth, Greece. In this LCA study of HTHP, the absence of detailed data on the control system, comprising components such as probes, flow meters, and related elements, has resulted in their exclusion from the analysis. Consistent with previous studies (Souliotis *et al.*, 2018), electronic components such as controls and sensors were excluded from the assessment. Only the essential components required for the typical operation of the analyzed systems were considered within the defined boundaries.

The LCI data as an input in SimaPro was gathered from a compilation of data provided by the project partner, namely the Enerin company. The inventory list of all materials used in the manufacturing stage of the Stirling Cycle HTHP system is presented in Table 1 for the innovative HTHP system. From the figure, it is evident that the main material of the Stirling HT heat pump is stainless steel, followed by non-alloy steel. Low-alloy steels and cast iron are the third and fourth most used materials.

Table 1: Inventory data for the Stirling Cycle-based HTHP system

Materials	Total amount (kg)
Non-alloy steel	3403.520
Stainless Steel	4135.833
Low-alloy steel	111.502
Cast iron	1041.58
Aluminium	348.19
Bronze	21.075
Brass	0.069
PTFE*	17.21
Graphite	1.26
Elastomer	9.066
Rubber	38.84
Copper	973.5
Epoxies	63

*PTFE: Polytetrafluoroethylene

2.2.2.2. Inventory data for the transport phase

This phase considers the environmental impacts linked to the transportation activities involved in assembling an HTHP. This LCI identifies and quantifies key inputs, such as transportation distance and mileage, to calculate the emissions generated from transporting the SC-HTHP components from the different suppliers to the manufacturing site at the Enerin Company in Norway. Heat pump installations in the Norwegian market largely rely on imported systems. The transportation data, provided by Enerin Company, indicates that the components and materials used to manufacture the HTHP are transported via sea, road, and air. This data for the transportation distance data for the components is presented in Table 1. The total transportation distance is calculated by multiplying the weight of all Stirling Cycle HTHP components by the total distance traveled from the suppliers to the Enerin Company for the manufacturing stage of the HTHP. The upstream transport by truck is modeled using EURO6 standards, while container ship transport follows the European transportation scenario. For air transport, European transportation is carried out using the medium-haul method, while international transport is conducted using the long-haul method. However, the travel distance is not specific to a single heat pump but is instead accounted for using the Ecoinvent database. In this approach, the transportation phase input of the HTHP materials within the SimaPro software is measured in tkm (ton.kilometer), reflecting emissions associated with a single unit according to the assessment of the environmental life cycle impacts of their transportation.

Table 2: Life cycle Inventory data for the transportation phase

From-to	Unit	Suppliers of raw materials to the manufacturing site
Transport by road	km	68726
Transport by sea	km	9660
Transport by air	km	39200

2.3. Inventory analysis and environmental assessment method

The LCA process can be significantly streamlined using specialized software, such as SimaPro, developed by PRe-Consultants B.V. (Netherlands). So, in this work, LCI is modeled using SimaPro (Version 9.6.0.1) software. Data for this paper is sourced from the Ecoinvent database (version 3.5) and supplemented with information provided by the Enerin Company. The analysis employs the ReCiPe 2016 Endpoint (H) method to assess environmental impacts. The main purpose of the method is to

convert the extensive list of LCI results into a simplified set of indicator scores, which represent the relative severity of each environmental impact category. ReCiPe indicators are assessed at two levels: 22 midpoint indicators and three endpoint indicators. The endpoint indicators represent environmental impacts at three broader levels: effects on human health, ecosystems, and resources. In the ReCiPe 2016 H method, as applied in SimaPro software for LCA, three key units used to quantify environmental impacts are DALY (Disability-Adjusted Life Years), species. yr (Species per Year) and USD 2013 (United States Dollar, 2013 value). The process involves characterization, normalization, and a final score (weighting) that quantifies the environmental impact of a product in eco-indicator points (Pt). One Pt denotes one-thousandth of the annual environmental effect of an average European resident (Dąbrowski and Dzikuć, 2012).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Overview of the environmental impact results

The LCA results in Figure 4 for the three damage categories reveal that in the manufacturing stage of the SC-HTHP, and the three transportation methods (ship, road, and air) used during the transport phase from the supplier to the manufacturing site, the most prominent environmental impact is on human health. The results showed that the total environmental impacts (kPt) during the manufacturing phase was 4.185 kPt while the impacts for transportation varied three methods: 0.00684 kPt for transport by ship, 0.0222 kPt for road transport, and 0.0033 kPt for transport by air, respectively (see Figure 4). The impact on the human health category (measured in kPt) is 4.117 for the manufacturing phase, 0.0068 for transport by air, 0.0222 for transport by road, and 0.0033 for transport by ship, as shown in Figure 4. Following human health, the next most substantial environmental impacts for two phases (manufacturing and transport) of the SC-HTHP are on ecosystems, followed by resources. The findings show that significant differences in the impact category values could be observed between the manufacturing and the transport phases across the categories of human health, ecosystems, and resources. However, the variations among the three transportation methods within the transport phase (ship, road, and air) are comparatively minor. In other words, among the three transportation methods, transport by road has the greatest environmental impact across the impact categories of human health, ecosystems, and resources, with respective impact values of 0.0209 kPt, 0.00069 kPt, and 0.00057 kPt, respectively (see Figure 4). This is because of the larger quantity and heavier weight of the components of heat pumps being transported by road, compared to those transported by air and ship. However, the results for impact categories for the transport phase are positive, indicating that the environmental impact within the three damage categories is minimal.

Figure 4: Three main damage categories of the SC-HTHP

Figure 5 illustrates the contribution of materials used in the components of the SC-HTHP system to the overall environmental impact. This analysis is based on the ReCiPe 2016 Endpoint (H) method, specifically for the scenario where the SC-HTHP system is manufactured at the Enerin Company. The assessment shows that steel, specifically chromium steel 18/8, accounts for the largest share of the total environmental impact of materials used in the components of the Stirling motor of the HTHP and A/C motor, contributing 34.432% with 1.452 kPts out of the total 4.218 kPts (see Figure 5). This is followed by cast iron, steel (unalloyed), Aluminum alloy AlLi, and copper (wire drawing), which contribute 26.941% (1.136 kPts), 19.992% (0.843 kPts), 8.777% (0.370 kPts), and 4.022% (0.169 kPts), respectively (see Figure 5). In addition, the results in Figure 5 demonstrate that graphite, brass and elastomer have the lowest shares of the overall environmental impact, respectively, contributing only minimal percentages to the overall 4.218 kPts. The emissions of chromium (VI) from iron production are harmful to humans and can lead to cancer. However, the processes involved in its extraction have a significant negative impact on environmental quality. A detailed analysis reveals that copper, primarily utilized within the electromotor of the Stirling cycle and also pipes, is the key material driving the impact categories. This is largely due to the significant direct atmospheric emissions of arsenic associated with copper production. Copper is recognized as one of the most toxic elements to aquatic species. While it is essential for growth, elevated concentrations can inflict irreversible damage on certain species. This harm propagates through the food chain, ultimately disrupting the entire ecosystem (Woody and O’Neal, 2012).

Figure 5: Contribution of materials applied in the SC-HTHP system and the transportation methods to the overall environmental impact

The comparison of characterization and damage assessment is given in Table 3, which shows the life cycle impacts associated with the manufacturing and transport phases of the HTHP. This table presents the LCA results across the 22 impact categories to specify which may be the source of potentially the largest number of environmental consequences in the two phases. The results indicate that the manufacturing stage has the most important impact across all 22 impact categories.

Furthermore, among the transportation methods in the transport phase, transport by road exhibits the highest impact in all impact categories. The findings reveal that the greatest environmental effect of the HTHP system occurs in the manufacturing stage, primarily due to fossil resource scarcity (1500.338 USD2013), followed by mineral resource scarcity (599.797 USD2013). Fossil resource scarcity also has a notable impact during the transportation phases, ranked in order of significance: road transport (80.499 USD2013), air transport (32.657 USD2013), and ship transport (4.531 USD2013). This result is consistent with the findings reported by [Dzikuć \(2013\)](#). However, after fossil resource scarcity and mineral resource scarcity, the greatest environmental effect of the manufacturing stage of the HTHP system is on human carcinogenic toxicity, followed by fine particulate matter formation, global warming, human health, and human non-carcinogenic toxicity. Other impact categories for the manufacturing and transport phases have a relatively limited impact on the environment, with their values being notably lower than those of the manufacturing stage impact categories. Steel, used in the outer shell of the heat exchanger, motor housing, rotor, and stator laminations of the A/C motor and heat pump, accounts for the highest contribution to global warming. This is primarily because of the high energy demands required for steel production via the blast furnace process. Coal, which serves as the main energy source for this process, significantly contributes to the materials used within the components of the heat pump and their overall impact on fossil resource scarcity and global warming ([Saoud et al., 2021](#)).

Table 3: Impact assessment and characterization for each impact category during the manufacturing and transport phase for the SC-HTHP

Impact category	Unit	Manufacturing phase	Transport by air	Transport by road	Transport by ship
Global warming, Human health	DALY	0.032074561	0.000226	0.000529	3.49×10^{-5}
Global warming, Terrestrial ecosystems	species.yr	9.67863×10^{-5}	6.83×10^{-7}	1.6×10^{-6}	1.05×10^{-7}
Global warming, Freshwater ecosystems	species.yr	2.64341×10^{-9}	1.86×10^{-11}	4.36×10^{-11}	2.87×10^{-12}
Stratospheric ozone depletion	DALY	3.99116×10^{-5}	7.05×10^{-9}	1.33×10^{-7}	9.46×10^{-9}
Ionizing radiation	DALY	1.18377×10^{-5}	6.14×10^{-9}	7.55×10^{-8}	1.47×10^{-9}
Ozone formation, Human health	DALY	7.91523×10^{-5}	9.91×10^{-7}	9.92×10^{-7}	6.43×10^{-7}
Fine particulate matter formation	DALY	0.061603542	0.000118	0.000286	0.000139
Ozone formation, Terrestrial ecosystems	species.yr	1.15505×10^{-5}	1.45×10^{-7}	1.6×10^{-7}	9.23×10^{-8}
Terrestrial acidification	species.yr	2.99649×10^{-5}	1.16×10^{-7}	1.75×10^{-7}	1.45×10^{-7}
Freshwater eutrophication	species.yr	1.24683×10^{-5}	3.22×10^{-9}	3.47×10^{-8}	1.12×10^{-9}
Marine eutrophication	species.yr	1.71025×10^{-9}	2.63×10^{-12}	1.36×10^{-11}	5.39×10^{-13}
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	species.yr	2.95988×10^{-5}	9.13×10^{-9}	1.93×10^{-7}	4.47×10^{-9}
Freshwater ecotoxicity	species.yr	3.64978×10^{-6}	4.48×10^{-10}	1×10^{-8}	2.58×10^{-10}
Marine ecotoxicity	species.yr	1.16885×10^{-6}	1.63×10^{-10}	3.43×10^{-9}	9.33×10^{-11}
Human carcinogenic toxicity	DALY	0.134639603	2.52×10^{-5}	0.000337	1.93×10^{-5}
Human non-carcinogenic toxicity	DALY	0.018114044	1.03×10^{-05}	0.000102	1.21×10^{-6}
Land use	species.yr	1.05882×10^{-5}	1.46×10^{-8}	3.85×10^{-7}	2.59×10^{-9}
Mineral resource scarcity	USD2013	599.7972824	0.025147	0.331426	0.017382
Fossil resource scarcity	USD2013	1500.338093	32.65723	80.49904	4.531625
Water consumption, Human health	DALY	0.000279098	1.34×10^{-7}	1.77×10^{-6}	3.93×10^{-8}
Water consumption, Terrestrial ecosystem	species.yr	1.54429×10^{-6}	1.14×10^{-9}	1.13×10^{-08}	2.85×10^{-10}
Water consumption, Aquatic ecosystems	species.yr	1.84462×10^{-10}	1.9×10^{-13}	1.05×10^{-12}	3.96×10^{-14}

Table 4 presents the footprint of the life cycle associated with the manufacturing and transport stages of the SC-HTHP system. The manufacturing stage has an average impact of 0.246842 DALY on human health, 0.000197 species·yr on ecosystems, and 2100.13 USD2013 on resources. Among the three transport methods, road transport exhibited the highest average impacts across all three endpoint categories: 0.001258 DALY for human health, 2.57×10^{-6} species·yr for ecosystems, and 80.830 USD2013 for resources.

Table 4: The environmental footprint of the SC-HTHP during its manufacturing and transport phases

Damage category	Unit	Manufacturing phase	Transport by air	Transport by road	Transport by Ship
Human health	DALY	0.246842	0.000381	0.001258	0.000195
Ecosystems	Species.yr	0.000197	9.73×10^{-7}	2.57×10^{-6}	3.51×10^{-7}
Resources	USD2013	2.100×10^3	32.682	80.830	4.549

4 CONCLUSIONS

The study assessed the environmental sustainability of an SC-HTHP by applying the detailed LCA methodology. The LCA was conducted for a functional unit of one SC-HTHP by applying the ReCiPe 2016 Endpoint (H) method as the environmental assessment approach. The results revealed notable differences in the impact category values between the manufacturing and transport phases, particularly across the categories of human health, ecosystem, and resources. In both phases, the highest impact was recorded in the human health category, followed by ecosystem quality and, subsequently, resources. The manufacturing stage is the largest contributor to the environmental effects of the SC High-Temperature Heat Pump, particularly in the categories of Fossil Resource Scarcity and Mineral Resource Scarcity, with impact values of 1500.338 USD2013 and 599.797 USD2013, respectively. However, further studies are recommended to explore the environmental effects of the SC-HTHP system using LCA by incorporating a broader dataset that includes the manufacturing, use, and end-of-life stages, along with waste treatment processes from end-users in various countries, conducting a Life cycle cost (LCC) assessment of the SC-HTHP could provide additional evidence supporting the heat pump's overall sustainability. Therefore, the LCA results offer key insights for stakeholders, including manufacturers and policymakers, to guide decisions on adopting environmentally efficient technologies. This approach supports component manufacturers and designers in making informed choices and optimizing products for commercialization.

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